

PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS WITH A HIGH LEVEL OF LANGUAGE PREPARATION

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Abstract. The novelty of the article is also provided by the comprehensive approach to the problem under consideration, which implies the interrelation of the main aspects of the pedagogical process described in the article, namely motivation, content and means of teaching. Considerable attention is also paid to the importance of the presence of authentic materials in the classroom, the main source of which today is the Internet and interactive forms of teaching using communicative methods of teaching language.

Keywords: linguodidactics, language training, level, criteria, communicative competence.

INTRODUCTION

In modern practice of teaching English to students, a teacher rarely encounters a situation where students have no experience of learning it at all. Indeed, English is studied in the vast majority of schools today. But even if a student studied another foreign language at school, it is still difficult to imagine an adult who is not familiar with English words and expressions at all, since English is currently the language of international communication, used, among other things, in the field of tourism. The English language has had a global status in a variety of areas of human activity for decades, for example, in the art of modern civilization. This is discussed in more detail in the articles by E. V. Aleshinskaya and E. S. Gritsenko. [1] and V. A. Potaturov [2]. On the other hand, in most cases, with the exception of leading linguistic universities and faculties, the basic level of language training of students is low these days. This is due to a number of reasons, both objective and subjective.

More details about the problems of the modern university as a social institution are described in the work of N.V. Osipova. [3]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Teachers who teach students not at universities, but at language centers, courses, and private practice face a similar situation. Those wishing to learn English begin to do so, if not from scratch, then from a low level. Among those studying English, there is a fairly common idea that if the level reached is above average, then there is no need to study with a teacher, but one should simply practice independently, including with native speakers. This point of view is highly controversial. Studying English under the guidance of a professional teacher has the following advantages over independent practice.

1) Systematicity. Classes are held regularly. This disciplines the student, he does not need to look for motivation in himself every time to study English.

2) Organization. The student does not need to independently select educational materials.

3) Purposefulness is a characteristic of any pedagogical process, in this case it consists in the purposeful formation of any specific knowledge, skills and abilities in English

4) Focus on the result, while with independent practice it is more important for the student to enjoy the process of using English.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In addition, it is psychologically important for many to understand that the activity they are involved in is managed by a professional. You can always ask the teacher any question, ask for clarification, although in the period of the development of the Internet, and in particular forums, this is becoming less relevant. One way or another, in our time there are a large number of manuals, textbooks, self-study guides and computer programs developed according to various methods, with the aim of helping those wishing to master English advance from an elementary to a more or less high level of language proficiency. However, the issue of teaching students

whose basic level is already significantly higher than average is poorly developed both from a theoretical and practical point of view. The most complex aspects of this issue will be given attention in the following chapters of the article.

Nowadays, in our country, the Western system of criteria for each level of language training, including advanced, is increasingly used. This system is universal and is used in courses, language centers, including preparation for international exams. In the domestic methodology of teaching a foreign language, the division into levels is much more arbitrary. It rather depends on the authors of each specific manual or course and on the vision and experience of each specific methodologist or teacher. A high level of proficiency in a foreign language can be understood as fluent free speech, that is, the absence of a language barrier, and the absence of grammatical errors in speech, and a rich vocabulary, and the use of a large number of idioms and set expressions. It seems to us that a high level of language implies, first of all, a high level of communicative competence, that is, good linguistic knowledge and the ability to productively use English in all types of speech activity: speaking, writing, reading and listening. In the modern dynamically developing multicultural world, as well as in the conditions of globalization, communicative competence is key for any modern specialist. As E.R. Gatiatullina and A.N. Orlov note, the state of modern civilization is perceived as nothing less than "threshold", as a threshold for the change of all forms of human activity from economic-technological and socio-structural to existential. Accordingly, the scale, pace (dynamics) and diversity of changes, which cover the basic spheres of life - culture, technology, cognitive practice, economics, socio-political organization, communicative relations - most often act as the main measures of human and social existence. [3] Defining the criteria for a high level of language proficiency is also difficult because it depends on the paradigm of the methodology in which the training is conducted. Traditional grammar-translation training puts language as a system at the forefront and is aimed primarily at developing reading and written translation skills. Communicative training is aimed primarily at communication and developing oral speech skills. Here we can give the

following example: one person can read English literature (including classics) without a dictionary, but at the same time experiences a colossal language barrier when meeting a foreigner. Another feels comfortable in a foreign language environment, but at the same time shows an average result on the school Unified State Exam, and both can reasonably claim that they have a good command of the language. Therefore, when determining the criteria for language proficiency, it is necessary to clearly understand what exactly is being assessed: language or speech. Currently, the prevailing idea is that all knowledge, skills and abilities should be harmoniously developed, since when using a language they are intertwined with each other, just as language and speech are interconnected.

In university practice, this problem is often complicated by the fact that the levels of students' language training, as a rule, should be tied to courses. If students of the language faculty study using Western textbooks, then they usually cover one level in each course. At the same time, the academic load, according to the curricula, is distributed between the courses almost equally. The duration of the courses is also the same. Thus, it turns out that the same pedagogical conditions are created for studying English at an advanced level and, say, at an intermediate level. The result of this contradiction is that textbooks in senior courses are simply not completed due to lack of time. The issue of the content of language training seems especially relevant at this level. Indeed, in practice, the task facing the teacher of "what to teach people who already speak English well" is sometimes difficult to resolve. Speaking about the content of teaching students with a high basic level of the language, the following points should be taken into account. Firstly, it is rare that students do not need educational programs at all, no matter what level of education they are at. Teaching practice shows that even at a very high level, students may have gaps in their knowledge at a much lower level. The fact is that language material, especially lexical, is practically inexhaustible, and it is impossible to study, much less remember everything. Secondly, there is always a need to expand the active vocabulary. Knowing a word does not mean being able to quickly use it in speech in the right

situation. A wide active vocabulary is the key to success in oral speech activities - in speaking and listening, when a person does not have the opportunity to think and remember a word. When working on grammar and vocabulary, you should always pay attention to the subtleties of the language that go beyond the rules that are already well known to students. You should concentrate on idioms, set expressions, phrases and ways of using that are not traditional for the language. It is important to work on enriching students' vocabulary with synonyms, which the English language is very rich in. In this regard, significant attention should be paid to style issues. For students, representatives of any specific professions, specialties or areas, it is necessary to study professional terminology, which can also be one of the important tasks at an advanced level of learning English.

CONCLUSION

So, we see that the problem of teaching students with a high basic level of English is very broad and multifaceted. It has not only purely methodological aspects, but also psychological and organizational ones. Nowadays, to work abroad or even in Uzbek international companies, candidates need international certificates confirming their fluency in English. This means that the problem considered in the article is relevant not only from a scientific but also from a practical point of view and is of an applied nature.

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